

Cross Sectional Imaging in Rabies Encephalitis: A Rare Entity

Ravneek Bawa¹, Prathamesh Naik², Ranjan Chandra³

¹Pg-Jr, ²Assistant Professor, ³Professor

Kanti Devi Medical College, Hospital & Research Centre, Mathura, U.P., India

Abstract

Rabies encephalitis is a severe and often fatal viral infection of the central nervous system caused by the rabies virus. This case report details the imaging features of a 32-year-old male who presented with history of fever and episodes of seizure following a dog bite to the scalp. Initial symptoms included fever, headache, and malaise, which rapidly progressed to confusion, agitation, and hydrophobia. Despite aggressive supportive care and administration of rabies immunoglobulin and the rabies vaccine, the patient's condition deteriorated, leading to death within two weeks of symptom onset. This case underscores the critical importance of identifying imaging features of rabies encephalitis for early diagnosis and prompt post-exposure prophylaxis in preventing rabies encephalitis, highlighting the need for increased awareness and vaccination efforts in high-risk areas.

Introduction

Rabies is a viral infection caused by an RNA virus belonging to the genus *Lyssavirus* of the family *Rhabdoviridae*. It is a rapidly progressive CNS infection, transmitted to humans by bite of an infected animal vector. It leads to rapidly progressive neurological deterioration and invariably progresses to death of the patient. Magnetic resonance imaging with contrast is the imaging of choice. Computed tomography can reveal some non-specific features however it is not diagnostic.

Case Presentation

A 32-year-old male presented to the casualty of KDMCH&RC, Mathura with complaints of fever since 5 days and an episode of seizure. On further inquiring, history of dog-bite was present on the scalp region about 20 to 25 days ago. Three doses of anti-rabies vaccine were administered after the bite. Upon general physical examination, patient had altered sensorium, drowsiness and irrelevant talking, increased muscular tone in all four limbs with hyper-reflexia was noted. Bilateral extensor planter responses were seen. However, no obvious signs of meningitis were seen.

The patient was taken up for cross-sectional imaging, four days after the initiation of symptoms, to rule out any neurological causes, for which a contrast enhanced CT scan followed by contrast enhanced MRI of brain was done. The CT scan (Figure 1) revealed non specific findings of diffuse cerebral edema, represented by diffuse effacement of cerebral sulci, cisterns and cerebellar foliae along with subtle leptomeningeal enhancement (Figure 2 & 3) involving bilateral temporal lobes.

Figure 1: NCCT Head; effaced cerebral sulci, Diffuse cerebral edema

Figure 2: CECT Brain supratentorial cut; Subtle meningeal enhancement at the background of diffuse cerebral edema

Figure 3: CECT Brain infratentorial cut; diffuse cerebral edema

On MR Imaging there were symmetrical hyperintense T2/FLAIR signal involving cortices of bilateral frontal and parieto-occipital lobes with effacement of adjacent sulci. Similar symmetrical hyperintense T2/FLAIR signal was also noted in bilateral basal ganglia (Figure 4 & 5), dorsal mid brain (Figure 6 & 7), pons and medulla (Figure 8 & 9). Patchy areas of symmetrical hyperintense T2/FLAIR signal noted in bilateral cerebellar hemispheres. Diffuse sulcal-FLAIR hyperintensities were also seen. There was diffuse leptomeningeal enhancement on post contrast T1-weighted images (Figure 10). Mild cerebral and cerebellar edema was noted. No evidence of hydrocephalus. No evidence of diffusion restriction on diffusion weighted imaging (DWI).

Figure 4: MRI Brain T2W image; Bilateral basal ganglia hyper intensities

Figure 5: MRI Brain FLAIR sequence- bilateral basal ganglia hyper intensities with cortical increased signals

Figure 6: MRI Brain T2W image- Hyperintensity in dorsal mid brain

Figure 7: MRI Brain- FLAIR sequence- Mid brain dorsal hyper intensity

Figure 8: MRI Brain T2W image- Hyperintensity in dorsal pons at the level of brachium pontis

Figure 9: MRI Brain- FLAIR sequence; hyper intensity in dorsal pons and medulla

Figure 10: MRI Brain T1W post contrast sequence showing subtle leptomeningeal enhancement

The neurological status of the patient continued to deteriorate. After 3 days, the patient expired. Considering the characteristic clinical presentation and rapid progression of the illness to death, laboratory confirmation of the disease was not obtained.

Discussion

Rabies encephalitis is a deadly infection of the central nervous system caused by the lyssavirus. While the diagnosis is primarily clinical, neuroimaging plays an important role in understanding the progression of the disease. Human rabies may present in one of the two types: Encephalitic and paralytic. Similar types are seen in dogs, namely, the furious and dumb type of rabies [1]. Known complications of rabies are collapse of respiratory system and pneumonitis, adult respiratory distress syndrome, type 1 diabetes, hypothermia, myocarditis, stress related gastrointestinal bleed and paralytic ileus. Pneumomediastinum secondary to rupture of the lower oesophagus occur towards terminal phase of disease, and are result of raised intra-thoracic pressure from repeated gag refluxes and respiratory muscle spasm associated with mechanical ventilation [2]. The 'encephalitic form' is commoner with hyperactivity, progressing rapidly to episodes of fluctuating consciousness as its classical features. Phobic spasms, aerophobia, and hydrophobia are the

classical symptoms that are accentuated by sounds or even the mention of water and puffs of air [3]. Paralytic rabies accounts for 20% of rabies. This review aims to summarize the current literature on various imaging modalities employed in the evaluation of rabies encephalitis.

Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI): MRI findings reveal ill-demarcated symmetrical areas of altered signal intensity in the brainstem appearing hyper intense on T2/FLAIR involving the dorsal aspect of the medulla, periaqueductal gray matter, collicular plate, dorsal pons as well as the central white matter of the midbrain, deep and cortical gray matter, deep and subcortical white matter, hippocampi, medial aspects of the thalami, and in the hypothalami on both sides of midline on T2W imaging [3,4]. Our case depicted similar findings on T2W imaging. Additionally, T2 hyperintensity were also seen in the bilateral basal ganglia and left temporoparietal and occipital cortices. Paralytic rabies can show increased signal intensity in medulla extending to cervical cord along with cord expansion [3]. Both the forms i.e. paralytic and encephalitic; have been reported to have similar distribution of signal alterations on MRI. The early post contrast phase reveal no enhancement of these structures. Mild-to-moderate post contrast enhancement of the hypothalamus, brainstem structures, and central gray matter of spinal cord can be seen as the disease progresses.

Positron Emission Tomography (PET): PET scans in rabies encephalitis reveal increased glucose metabolism in affected areas, depicting neuroinvasion and neuronal destruction. Therefore, PET can help in early detection and localization of rabies encephalitis, assisting clinicians in differentiating it from other encephalopathies.

Computed Tomography (CT): CT being less sensitive, reveals nonspecific findings such as cerebral edema and atrophy in later stages of the disease. Bilateral symmetric, non-enhancing hypodense lesions within the capsule-ganglionic region can be additional findings. Brainstem and hypothalamus are other regions of the brain involved by rabies encephalitis which are not well assessed by CT scan.

Conclusions

Neuroimaging is integral in the diagnosis and understanding of rabies encephalitis. While MRI is the imaging modality of choice, PET and CT provide insights, highlighting the need for a multimodal approach in comprehensive patient management. Early diagnosis of rabies cannot cause significant alterations in patient prognosis, but it enables prompt institution of public health measures.

References

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